

THE PROBLEM OF TEXT IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. Language is an extraordinarily unique phenomenon as a central and at the same time extremely complex object of study of old and new sciences that explore the essence, psyche and human activity from different angles. The path of direct awareness and manifestation of this mysterious phenomenon is to divide the entire flow of speech into parts, to divide it into pieces, to be able to imagine each part or particles separately, and also to be able to perceive proportional and even disproportionate relationships between these parts or particles, there is no doubt that his mind went through a long and difficult path of gradual improvement. Undoubtedly, the place of communication and dialogue between people is very important when they unite as separate peoples as a society of people and regularly go on the path of development, called civilization. It is impossible to imagine a human society completely free from communicative activity, and whose members are completely deprived of the possibility of mutual communication.

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For thousands of years, the human child learns, teaches, collects, stores and passes on his experience to others. Of course, all these activities, without exception - training, collecting and accumulating experience and information, receiving and transmitting them from others are carried out through linguistic communication (oral and written). Today, not only specialists, but everyone knows that the main task of the language is a communicative task. However, the linguo-logical, socio-spiritual, historical and aesthetic mechanisms of this communicative communication, speech communication, the rules and features associated with them have not been fully studied by the relevant sciences (such as linguistics, literary criticism, logic, sociology, aesthetics). Despite the fact that many problems in this regard have always been in the center of attention of scientists, they are still the cause of controversy and discussion, the different opinions expressed are sometimes recognized by some people, and sometimes cause serious objections.

Naturally, in the emergence and implementation of any speech communication, the participation of three main elements is mandatory, that is, the speaker (writer) - information (text) - listener (reader). True, in speech communication the role of the speech environment, the channel for transmitting information (voice, writing, magnetic recording, telephone), the status, age and other characteristics of the participants in communication, as well as various other non-scientific tools, is extremely important, even often decisive. But these three elements are the main pillars of verbal communication, without one of them the process of communication cannot take place.

Linguistics naturally gave priority to the problem of linguistic expression and understanding of information, which is the main subject of "giving and receiving" between the two parties (speaking, listening) in the process of communication. After all, the ultimate and main goal of any communication is the "movement" of this information, and this "movement" is carried out through language. That is why linguistics was looking for the same basic and large unit of "information in motion", as a result of which speech was recognized as such a large unit for a long time.

It is known that linguistics has divided its object of study into separate sections, that is, sounds (phonemes) are studied in phonetics-phonology, morphemes in morphology, lexemes in lexicology, and simple and complex sentences in syntax. We can say that in traditional linguistics the highest and last unit at the highest level of the language is considered as a sentence. According to the Polish linguist M. R. Mayenova, the judgment that "linguistics ends its observations where speech ends" was until recently considered an open truth. Texts consisting of many sentences are excluded from the observation of this field of science, entirely limited by the framework of grammar in the broadest sense.⁴⁴

Indeed, if "linguistics ends its observations where speech ends", that is, considers the sentence only as a communicative unit, then such linguistics will easily and completely penetrate into the semantic-communicative essence of the sentence. It is impossible to know the linguistic-logical core of any single sentence. Just as the meaning of any word takes on reality in a particular context, it is difficult to objectively assess the meaning of a sentence apart from its relation to other sentences. Consider the most common example: to understand the content of the sentence *Tourists will go to that city tomorrow*, there should be a sentence that was used (or can be used) before it, for example, *a film about the historical monuments of the city of Samarkand is shown*. It seems that the first sentence cannot be considered a completely independent communicative unit, therefore the boundary of linguistics should not end here, but go beyond it. It is known that the interpretation of syntax only in the form of the doctrine of the sentence (and the phrase) was the pillar of this limitation. However, it has long

⁴⁴ The quote is taken from this article: Janus E. Review of Polish works on text structure / Text syntax. - M.: Nauka, 1979, p. 325.

been understood that the view of syntax as a "science of the structure of speech" sheds light on many problems.⁴⁵

Coherent speech, holistic speech work, the study of the text, that is, the approach to the text in the form of a sentence-period-large fragment-holistic whole began from ancient times - Aristotle and his followers.⁴⁶

The development of the concept of text in Russian linguistics dates back to the 40s of the last century. In 1947, A. I. Belich, in his article on the classification of linguistic sciences, emphasized that in the grammatical description of linguistic facts, a special place should be given to a whole chain of sentences related on the basis of a common meaning and manifested in the form of a certain syntactic-semantic integrity, and this is decisive importance for the emergence of the concept of "text", and drew attention to the fact that it is possessive, and emphasized the feasibility of studying interactions and connections in such a chain of sentences at the syntactic faculty of linguistics.⁴⁷ In almost the same years, especially in 1949, the question of large units of speech, that is, of "sentence cooperation", was raised in German linguistics. In his study of the most important means that structurally form relationships between sentences, such as lexical repetition, articles, pronouns, ellipsis, verb tenses, repeated conjunctions, interrogative words, K. Boost writes: "So many threads stretch from one sentence to another that they form such a dense web that we can talk about the interweaving of sentences, their interweaving as a single web, because each individual sentence is closely connected with others".⁴⁸

Since the second half of the 60s of the last century, the field of "text linguistics" has entered a period of rapid development. The text as an integral speech unit and its constituent elements, factors and characteristics were studied from different positions. A kind of, so to speak, huge "hype" has arisen around this area. Even some experts considered text linguistics not a separate area of linguistics, but the foundation, the basis of linguistics as a whole. In the countries of Western Europe, periodicals and scientific collections on the linguistics of the text were published, special scientific teams were formed, monographs were published, textbooks and even textbooks for schools were published.⁴⁹

The merits of the Czech (representatives of the Prague Linguistic Circle), German, French, English, American, Dutch, Polish and other schools of linguistics in the general formation and development of text theory, text linguistics are recognized in world

⁴⁵ See: Dolgova O.V. Syntax as the science of speech construction. - M.: Higher school, 1980.

⁴⁶ See about it: Bart R. Text Linguistics / New in Foreign Linguistics. Issue. 8. Linguistics of the text. -M.: Progress, 1978, p. 444-445.

⁴⁷ Belich A.I. On the question of the distribution of grammatical material in the main grammatical disciplines / Bulletin of Moscow State University, 1947, N 7, p. 22.

⁴⁸ See about this: Moskalskaya O.I. Grammar of the text. -M.: Higher School, 1981, p. 5-6.

⁴⁹ See about it: Nikolaeva T.M. Linguistics of the text. Current state and prospects / New in foreign linguistics. Issue. 8. Linguistics of the text. -M.: Progress, 1978, p. 5-39..

linguistics and are constantly mentioned in scientific research.⁵⁰ In Russian linguistics, many linguists, such as V.V. Odintsov, I.R. Galperin, O.I. Moskalskaya, L.M. Loseva, Yu.M. Lotman, Z.Ya. N.D. Zarubina, E.V. Sidorov, O.L. Kamenskaya, A.I. Gorshkov, N.S. Valgina.⁵¹ O. I. Moskalskaya, who carefully analyzed the studies of this trend in linguistics, said that by the 60s and 70s of the last century, interest in the linguistic study of the text had increased enormously, an unprecedented number of studies on text linguistics appeared in world linguistics, and text linguistics as a linguistic science in its own right was full of emphasis on recognition, summarizes the main principles underlying this recognition in research, by grouping as follows:

1. The basic unit of speech expressing a complete thought is not a sentence, but a text; speech-thought is only a special case, a special type of text. The text is the highest unit of the syntactic level.

2. Specific speech works - texts are built on the general principles of constructing texts; these principles concern the language system or the authority of language, not the realm of speech. Given these aspects, the text should be considered not only as a unit of speech, but also as a unit of language.

3. The text, like other linguistic units, is part of the linguistic sign system.

4. A comprehensive study of the text as a speech and language unit of a separate level requires the creation of a special science within the framework of linguistics - text linguistics.

O. M. Moskalskaya draws attention to the fact that these rules, especially the rules of the first paragraph, were repeated in various forms in the studies of that time, and “found a response as a battle slogan of a new linguistic direction”, and gives examples of such opinions of Western scientists: “ We usually do not use individual words, but sentences and speak in texts ”(G. Weinrich). “If we speak, we speak only in texts” (P. Hartman). “Language is only a means of communication between people in the form of texts and in the task of creating texts” (P. Hartman). “When we use language, the basic unit is not a word or a sentence, but a text” (M. A. K. Halliday). “Today it is becoming generally recognized that the highest and most independent unit of language is not speech, but text” (W. Dressler).⁵²

⁵⁰ See about it: New in foreign linguistics. Issue. 8. Linguistics of the text. –M.: Progress, 1978; Moskalskaya O.I. Quoted work, pp. 6-12; Galperin I.R. Text as an object of linguistic research. –M.: Nauka, 1981, p. 5-7; Dijk van T.A., Kinch V. Strategies for understanding a connected text / New in foreign linguistics. Issue. 23. Cognitive aspects of language. –M.: Progress, 1988, p.153-211 and others.

⁵¹ Lotman Yu.M. The structure of the artistic text. –M.: Art, 1970; Linguistics of the text. Materials of scientific conference. Ch. I, II. -M., 1974; Loseva L.M. How the text is built. –M.: Enlightenment, 1980; Odintsov V.V. Text style. - M.: Nauka, 1980; Moskalskaya O.I. said work; Galperin I.R. said work; Zarubina N.D. Text: linguistic and methodological aspects. -M.: Russian language, 1981; Turaeva Z.Ya. Linguistics of the text. –M.: Enlightenment, 1986; Sidorov E.V. Problems of speech system. –M.: Nauka, 1987; Kamenskaya O.L. Text and communication. -M.: Higher school, 1990; Gorshkov A.I. Russian style. -M.: Astrel-AST, 2001, p. 53-258; Valgina N.S. Text theory. –M.: Logos, 2004 and others.

⁵² Moskalskaya O.I. Quoted work, p. 9.

This is how the linguistics of the text is formed and developed. But in Russian linguistics there is no shortage of critical opinions, such as the fact that text linguistics covers too many issues in its field of study, interferes with the problems of other areas of science, allegedly denies the concept of a sentence. For example, the well-known Russian philologist R. A. Budagov wrote about the publication⁵³ of a collection of studies on text linguistics, created by a number of specialists from all over the world: "To what extent is text linguistics linguistics?" In his article, text linguistics attempts to study the human ability to create, structure, understand, compose and perceive the compositional integrity of the text, while he counters that this takes on the tasks of other disciplines. In case of text size limitation, it says that the path of this direction is not correct.⁵⁴ He writes: The original intentions of the creators of Linguistics of the Text were very good. Responding to scientific and technological progress, the requirements of the information age. Show that the language has not only small units, but also large ones. The study of forms and ways of connecting sentences in a text flow. All this is worthy of attention and should be supported. Another thing - the desire not to be likened in all respects to the so-called traditional linguistics - causes fundamental objections... A more fragile, weak point is the opposition of large and small units of the language. At the same time, it is impossible to study the principles of connecting sentences without examining not only the structure of a sentence, word or phrase, but without even being interested in it ...⁵⁵

Such objections cannot be accepted, since text linguistics, considering the text as the main unit, does not deny the existence of sentences or phrases, their features, their place in the text, in general, the rules recognized as the achievements of traditional linguistics. These objections and critical opinions are appropriately understood as an invitation to remember the need to approach existing problems more carefully and vigilantly. The question of the text in Turkic studies was first raised in the early 70s of the last century by the famous Tatar linguist M. Zakiyev. First of all, he states that the study of connected speech is impossible without studying the relationship between independent sentences, because connected speech always consists of a chain of sentences connected to each other in various ways, and, accordingly, the so-called "complex syntactic whole" is formed in connected speech, units, which are large and complex, stand out from the sentence (they are part of a paragraph, a paragraph, an entire chapter, sometimes even a whole work, and so on) and writes: "Isolation of a complex syntactic whole in a coherent speech suggests a purely methodological goal; it cannot be the main unit of speech and cannot be opposed to the main sentence".⁵⁶ In

⁵³ New in foreign linguistics. Issue. 8. Linguistics of the text. –M.: Progress, 1978

⁵⁴ Budagov R.A. Philology and culture. –M.: MGU, 1980, p. 78-80.

⁵⁵ Quoted book, p. 85.

⁵⁶ Modern Tatar language. –M.: Nauka, 1971, p. 237.

his textbook, published in 1974, he calls complex syntactic integers “syntactic integers” (“syntactic bötennar”) and writes the following: “The study of syntactic integers, that is, the connection of independent sentences, has not yet received full development in the Turkic languages. However, this question is very important not only for the science of language, but also for the science of literature. Because, without knowing the connection of independent sentences, it is very difficult to compose a complete organized whole of a text, a work, a separate part of it, a paragraph”.⁵⁷ In a textbook published in 1984, the scientist dwelled in detail on the problems of text linguistics and recognized that the text is a coherent unit. He included a special section in the book called "Text Syntax", which contains opinions on such issues as text types, text content, communicative, structural, grammatical integrity, text composition, text syntax, and linguistic categories.⁵⁸

The question of the syntax of the text and its features in Azerbaijani linguistics was studied by K. M. Abdullayev in a monographic plan. The text in the Azerbaijani language, its communicative, structural and semantic features, text units are analyzed on the basis of existing views and original observations.⁵⁹ In Uzbek linguistics, a lot of work has been done on the text and its research. Academician G. Abdurakhmanov, one of the first in Uzbek linguistics, made a presentation on text theory at the III Conference of Turkic Studies of the former Union, held in Tashkent on September 10-12, 1980 and gave a lecture on text theory, expressed his opinion on the essence and solutions of the problem, identified a number of types of text.⁶⁰

The great linguist A. Gulomov expressed his valuable opinion on the essence of the text. As a comprehensive scientist, constantly keeping abreast of the processes taking place in world linguistics, he cannot avoid the issue of the text, reworking and supplementing the third edition of the textbook "Modern Uzbek literary language, Syntax" (co-authored with M. Askarova), although in a compressed form, brings his views on the text into the book. A. Gulomov emphasizes that the completeness of thought in a sentence is relative, the completeness of the content in a work is understood from the entire text, he gives an example of a complete text consisting of three paragraphs, and on its basis writes the following: “1. The expression of opinion is not limited to the scope of the sentence (simple sentence and compound sentence). The complete representation usually gives a syntactic integer that is larger than the sentence. The word is one of its components as part of the whole. 2. This component will be related to the other components of this whole in all respects (content, grammar)

⁵⁷ Зәкиев М.З. Хәзерге татар әдәби теле (Синтаксис). -Казан, 1974, 257-бит.

⁵⁸ Зәкиев М.З. Хәзерге татар әдәби теле синтаксисы һәм пунктуациясе. -Казан: Татарстан китап нәшрияты, 1984, 199-226-битләр.

⁵⁹ Abdullaev K.M. Theoretical problems of the syntax of the Azerbaijani language: Abstract of the thesis of a doctor of philological sciences. - Baku, 1984, p. 33-43.

⁶⁰ See about this: III All-Union Turkological Conference // Soviet Turkology. -Baku, 1981, N1, p.93.

through various means. Own composition and stylistic features will be preserved. 3. A simple sentence can itself form a paragraph under certain conditions... 4. The text is considered to be such a syntactic whole, a syntactic construction. A separate sentence is a relatively complete thought, the text is the content of the whole complex. 5. Because the text is a single entity, it may have some headings that match its content. The text is divided into several segments - parts (some fragments, paragraphs, sentences). Thus, the text shows even more clearly that language is a means of communication. Speech is displayed as text. 6. Text is a large piece of speech, and a paragraph is a piece of text. All forms of text (maximum text and minimum text) fully represent a particular topic (content). So, this is a high-level syntactic unit...

Given these features of the text, some researchers consider it necessary to single it out as an independent area of linguistics (with such names as text grammar, text linguistics). Some call it text syntax (e.g., phrase syntax, simple sentence syntax) and see it as a continuation of sentence syntax, thereby expanding the meaning of the term syntax, emphasizing that it should be considered as a basic syntactic unit, a larger syntactic whole than a sentence: where the top the syntax boundary is the syntax of the text, not the syntax of the compound sentence. Most reviewers cover this area at a glance.

The syntax of the text in Uzbek linguistics has not yet been studied.”⁶¹ As can be seen, A. Gulomov clearly showed the nature and essence of the text, based on the facts of the Uzbek language and taking into account the various points of view of world linguistics. The provisions mentioned one after the other in these six paragraphs contain the main general features of the text. In his Ph.D. thesis, M. Tukhsanov investigated the system of means linking the elements of microtext in the Uzbek language, distinguishing between macrotext and microtext.⁶² However, it should be noted that although the researcher set himself the goal of studying the microtext in artistic speech, the work considered the coherence of the microtext as a whole, that is, attention is not focused on aspects related to the uniqueness of the text in artistic speech. But, despite this, this work is remarkable in that it is one of the first studies devoted to the monographic aspect of the microtext and its coherence in Uzbek linguistics.

One of the first generalizing, educational works on text linguistics in Uzbek linguistics was created by A. Mamajonov. His special course "Text Linguistics", intended for students of philology, analyzes scientific views on the text, the essence, types and units of the concept of text, the connection and connecting means of these

⁶¹ Gulomov A., Askarova M. Modern Uzbek literary language. Syntax. - Tashkent: Uchitel, 1987. p. 6-7.

⁶² Tukhsanov M. Microtext and the system of expressing its coherence in Uzbek artistic speech: Abstract of the thesis of a candidate of philological sciences. -Tashkent, 1987.

units, synonymy between units of the text, describes syntactic-stylistic figures.⁶³ Later, in the textbook *Syntax of the Text*, published in collaboration with his student M. Abdupattoev, the structural-semantic and stylistic aspects of the text, thematic-rhematic relations in text units were carefully analyzed and appropriate conclusions were drawn.⁶⁴ N. Turniyozov's textbook entitled "Text Linguistics" is one of such educational works, which provides scientific information on topics such as general information about the text, the concepts of micro- and macrotext, various relationships between text elements in accordance with the relevant curriculum.⁶⁵ In subsequent years, a number of scientific articles were also published related to the study of one or another aspect of the text problem in Uzbek linguistics.⁶⁶

The German linguist R. Harweg, one of the foreign activists in the study of text problems and the creation of its integral scientific theory, stated in 1974 that it would take at least a hundred years for text linguistics to fully settle in linguistics.⁶⁷ But today it is not even 40 years since this statement was made. But all over the world, regular and intensive serious scientific research, as a natural result of research, whether it is "text linguistics" ("text theory") or "text grammar" ("text syntax"), such a direction is its formation as a separate science and academic subject generally accepted and not denied by anyone.

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⁶³ Mamajonov A. *Linguistics of the text*. -Tashkent, 1989.

⁶⁴ Mamazhonov A., Abdupattoev M. *Text syntax*. - Ferghana, 2002.

⁶⁵ Turniyozov N. *Linguistics of the text (text of lectures)*. - Samarkand, 2004.

⁶⁶ For example: Tukhsanov M. *Microtext and its communicative integrity // Uzbek language and literature*, 1990, N5, p. 66-69; Shakhobiddinova Sh., Isakov Z. *Text and one of its connecting means // Uzbek language and literature*, 2004, N6, p. 75-76; Mukhamedova D. *In the form of a microtext, the introduction of subordinate clauses into equal contact // Uzbek language and literature*, 2004, N6, p. 90-91; Mukhamedova D. *Text and its types / Independence and language*. Part 3. - Tashkent, 2007. p. 17-19.

⁶⁷ See about this: Turniyozov N. *Quoted work*, p. 15.

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